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Electron-gamma decay spectroscopy of ^{152}Tb

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Terbium-152, decaying by electron capture and β^+ emission to ^{152}Gd with $Q_{EC} = 3990(40)$ keV and $T_{1/2} = 17.8784(95)$ h, shows promise in nuclear medicine. First-in-human trials have demonstrated its suitability for positron emission tomography (PET) imaging, with potential applications in personalised cancer treatments through its membership of the terbium theragnostic quartet. A source of ^{152}Tb was produced at CERN-ISOLDE, using spallation of a tantalum target induced by a 1.4 GeV proton beam and mass separation with the ISOL method. The source was then shipped to ILL Grenoble for measurement. This paper details the electron-gamma spectroscopy of the decay using the PN1/LOHENGRIN setup, supporting the gamma-gamma spectroscopy of ^{152}Tb sources produced in the same ISOLDE run. Preliminary measurements of the relative intensity of internal conversion electrons are presented, validating theoretical predictions of internal conversion coefficients for several transitions and confirming their assigned multipolarity. The final analysis will support the gamma-gamma spectroscopy in establishing a revised level scheme for the decay, leading to an updated beta strength function and a corresponding change in dosimetry calculations.

1. Introduction

Theranostics is a method of personalised cancer treatment combining diagnostics and therapy into a unified approach. Nuclear medicine provides both components through different types of radioactive decay, with potential theragnostic pairings available in the form of isotopes of the same element with different decay properties.

The terbium theragnostic quartet, composed of $^{149,152,155,161}\text{Tb}$, provides two diagnostic and two therapeutic decay modes. As all isotopes of an element have the same chemical properties, these are therefore compatible with the same delivery mechanisms [1]. The uptake of the delivery vector at the site of the tumour can be measured using the imaging isotope before the therapeutic component is administered. This allows the treatment plan to be tuned to each individual patient, based on a direct measurement of the behaviour of the targeting molecule in the body [2].

Terbium-152 is a diagnostic component of the quartet, used in positron emission tomography (PET) imaging. The $J^\pi = 2^+$ ground state decays by β^+ emission and electron capture to ^{152}Gd with $T_{1/2} = 17.8784(95)$ h [3] and $Q_{EC} = 3990(40)$ keV [4]. First-in-human trials have demonstrated good performance in imaging neuroendocrine and prostate cancers, delivered to patients using different targeting molecules [5, 6].

Before ^{152}Tb can be used routinely, a traceable standardisation of the decay must be established to allow the radiation dose to be quantified for each patient. This depends on accurate nuclear data, particularly the positron, gamma, and electron emission intensities I_{β^+} , I_γ , and I_{e^-} respectively. A comprehensive level scheme aids greatly in determining these quantities, but the nuclear data describing the decay of ^{152}Tb is limited.

The latest evaluation of the decay took place in 2013 [4], with the most recent data taken from a 2003 study using a pair of high purity germanium (HPGe) detectors to perform gamma-gamma coincidence spectroscopy [7]. The highest energy excited state reported in ^{152}Gd following the decay is at 3358 keV, more than 600 keV below the Q_{EC} , suggesting that there may be further weakly populated excited states that have not yet been identified. This suggestion is supported by the large number of unplaced transitions in the evaluated data, with only 387 out of 635 identified transitions placed on the level scheme [8]. A 2014 PhD thesis also identified several high-energy excited states, but these results have not been included in the evaluated decay data [9].

The inability of previous experiments to identify weakly populated high energy states is due to the pandemonium effect: high-resolution gamma-ray detectors have limited efficiency at high energies, and it is therefore challenging to detect the gamma rays depopulating these states. These unidentified high-energy excited states are populated by low-energy beta decays, the direct measurement of which is challenging in such a complex decay scheme. With the density of states increasing with excitation energy, a significant proportion of the beta decay strength is to these high-energy states and is therefore unmeasured [10]. Consequently, current dosimetry calculations rely on nuclear data that does not consider beta decays to these states.

Similar revisions of the beta decay strength have taken place following recent studies of other β^+ -decaying medical isotopes, leading to relative changes of over 10% in the calculated beta dose following gamma-gamma spectroscopy of these decays [8, 11]. A new spectroscopy of the decay of ^{152}Tb is therefore necessary to address this limitation in the nuclear data, using a high-efficiency gamma-ray detector array.

In addition to gamma spectroscopy, measurements of conversion electrons emitted in this decay are important for fully establishing the decay scheme. Conversion electrons represent a further contribution to the dose received by patients, with the short range of electrons meaning that a much greater proportion of the radiation energy is deposited in the patient's body compared to gamma rays. Accurate internal conversion coefficients are also important for balancing feeding in and out excited states, which may have significant implications for the beta strength function and dosimetry calculations. While these may be calculated theoretically [12], internal conversion coefficients depend on the multipolarity of electromagnetic transitions which may be verified by direct measurement of the conversion electrons.

The presently adopted nuclear data for this decay recommends internal conversion coefficients calculated using theoretical predictions [4]. While many transitions following the decay of ^{152}Tb have had their internal conversion coefficient measured previously in a 1970 study [13], these values have limited precision compared to theoretical results and have not been adopted in the evaluated nuclear data. This paper presents preliminary results of electron-gamma coincidence spectroscopy of the decay of ^{152}Tb , with the aim of the completed project to validate these predicted internal conversion coefficients and improve their precision where possible.

2. Experiment

Sources of ^{152}Tb were produced at CERN-ISOLDE, using a 1.4 GeV proton beam to induce spallation on a tantalum target. The reaction products diffuse out of the hot target into the tantalum ioniser, both at temperatures of approximately 2000 °C. Resonant laser ionisation of the radioactive precursor ^{152}Dy was carried out, allowing for increased cumulative yields of ^{152}Tb . The ions were accelerated to 30 keV and mass-separated by deflection in a magnetic dipole selecting for $A = 152$, and the products implanted into a metallised Mylar foil. The samples were allowed to decay from ^{152}Dy to ^{152}Tb , then delivered to ILL for measurement [14]. The first measurement of this source began approximately 70 hours after collection at CERN, allowing the small admixture of ^{152m}Eu in the sample to decay to <1% relative to the ^{152}Tb .

Electron-gamma spectroscopy of the source was carried out using the LOHENGRIN/PN1 conversion electron spectroscopy setup. This array consists of a liquid-nitrogen-cooled HPGe clover paired with two 4 mm thick lithium-drifted silicon (Si(Li)) detectors, with the clover most sensitive to gamma rays and the Si(Li) detectors allowing for detection of electrons and x-rays. One of the two Si(Li) detectors was not functional at the time of the experiment, but the reduced array configuration was still sufficient for electron-gamma coincidence analysis. While the setup has only recently been used in this form, previous experiments have used a similar array configuration consisting of only a single Si(Li) detector and a pair of HPGe clovers, placed downstream of the Lohengrin mass separator [15].

The detector setup and sample were kept under vacuum for the duration of the experiment, preventing scattering of the emitted electrons in air between the sample and the detector. This made calibrating the setup challenging as changing the sample requires returning the setup to atmospheric pressure and room temperature, a process that is both impractical and involves such significant changes in temperature and pressure that the array operational conditions could not be guaranteed to remain constant between calibration and measurement. For this reason, the detector efficiency was modelled through Monte Carlo simulations and will be validated using electron-gamma coincidence analysis. A Monte Carlo simulation of the setup predicts a full-energy peak

efficiency of approximately 8.6% at 344 keV for the HPGe clover, and $\sim 4.6\%$ for 291 keV electrons with the Si(Li) detector. However, while the efficiency curve remains unvalidated, all peak intensities will be quoted relative to the 344 keV transition K-shell electron peak, and the relative efficiency will be assumed to be constant over the range of energies examined here based on preliminary Monte Carlo simulations and the efficiency curves of Si(Li) detectors of similar thicknesses [16].

The Fission Product Prompt γ -ray Spectrometer (FIPPS), an array of 64 HPGe gamma-ray detectors [17, 18], was used to perform gamma-gamma coincidence spectroscopy of a pair of ^{152}Tb sources from the same ISOLDE production run. The gamma-gamma coincidence spectroscopy measurements are presented in a separate paper [19], with preliminary analysis resulting in the identification of multiple previously unreported excited states and the first placement of many discrete-energy gamma rays into the level scheme.

3. Data analysis

The decaying source was measured for approximately 37.5 h in the array, recording 1.8×10^8 events in the clover and 5.4×10^7 events in the Si(Li) detector. Clover events were reconstructed off-line using addback, summing the energies of events recorded in any of the four HPGe crystals within a window of ± 150 ns. A coincidence window of ± 200 ns was applied to clover-Si(Li) events in off-line analysis, resulting in 1.5×10^6 total coincidence events. The energy responses of the detectors were calibrated using previously known transitions in the decay of ^{152}Tb . A selection of low-lying excited states populated in the decay are presented in the partial level scheme in figure 1.

Electron-gamma coincidence analysis was used to improve the ability of the array to detect weak conversion electron peaks. Coincidence gates were set on gamma rays using the HPGe clover, with a Compton background subtracted to produce the gated spectra. This greatly reduced the level of background radiation in the spectra, improving the peak to total ratio of the conversion electron peaks.

4. Results

Figure 2 shows the spectrum collected from the Si(Li) detector, featuring strong conversion electron peaks. Conversion electrons are emitted with kinetic energies equal to the transition energy minus the electron binding energy, which is the energy needed to liberate an electron from its host atom. As the binding energy varies depending on the shell from which the electron originated, discrete-energy conversion electron peaks can be seen corresponding to these shells. The K-shell and L-shell binding energies in gadolinium are 50.25 keV and 8.21 keV respectively, and so the K and L conversion electron peaks are offset from each transition energy

correspondingly. Prominent peaks visible on the singles spectrum (summarised in the level scheme in figure 1) include the K- and L-shell conversion electrons emitted from strong transitions such as the 344 keV $2^+ \rightarrow 0^+$, 271 keV $0^+ \rightarrow 2^+$, and 586 keV $2^+ \rightarrow 2^+$. Also featured are E0 $0^+ \rightarrow 0^+$ transitions at 433 keV and 615 keV, and 1048 keV. Despite the lower overall transition intensity compared to other strong peaks, E0 transitions have zero single-gamma-ray intensity and so represent a significant proportion of the conversion electron emissions.

The gamma-ray spectrum collected from the HPGe clover is also shown in figure 2. Both the initial and final excited states involved in the 433 keV and 615 keV E0 transition have $J^\pi = 0^+$, and as such they have no single-gamma-ray decay mode. As a result, this transition cannot be detected using gamma-ray detectors, and no peaks are observed at the corresponding transition energies marked on the bottom spectrum in figure 2.

The intensities of the K-shell electron peaks for both the 433 keV and 615 keV transitions have been measured in the singles spectrum, and are given in table 1 relative to the K-shell electron intensity of the 344 keV transition. Predicted intensity ratios have been calculated using previous measurements of the E0 intensities, as well as the previously measured 344 keV gamma-ray intensity and the BrICC predicted K-shell internal conversion coefficient for the 344 keV transition, all taken from the nuclear data sheets [4]. Although these preliminary measurements do not take into account any differences in detector efficiency over this range of energies, the E0 intensities correspond closely to the values adopted in the nuclear data sheets, validating the adopted values. The same comparison is made for the 586 keV mixed E0+M1+E2 transition, which also validates the adopted internal conversion coefficient.

Electron-gamma coincidences have been used to improve the ability of the array to measure low-intensity radiation against the background as demonstrated in figure 3. Prominent conversion electron peaks from the

Table 1. Preliminary E0 K-shell transition intensities, given relative to the K-shell electron peak from the 344 keV transition. The intensity ratio for the 586 keV mixed E0+M1+E2 transition is also given. Literature ratios are calculated from previously measured E0 and 344 keV gamma-ray intensities, and the BrICC predicted 344 keV K-shell internal conversion coefficient, all reported in the nuclear data sheets [4].

E (keV)	I_K/I_{344} (measured)	I_K/I_{344} (literature)
615	0.551(16)	0.565(28)
433	0.234(8)	0.229(25)
586	0.0861(20)	0.094(10)

344 keV and 615 keV transitions, seen in the singles spectrum, are removed in the 344 keV coincidence gate, allowing less-intense discrete-energy conversion electron peaks to be seen. The gate on the 271 keV gamma ray shows the 344 keV and 433 keV peak, removing the 271 keV and 586 keV transitions seen in the 344 keV gate, demonstrating the selectivity available from coincidence gating and its ability to examine deexcitation cascades. The peak to total ratio of some of these peaks are greatly improved in the coincidence gates, and the large electron continuum below 200 keV is significantly reduced. However, the limited statistics still hinder the detectability of the lower intensity peaks, for example the (L+M) components of the 433 keV and 586 keV transitions seen in the 344 keV gate in figure 3 which are challenging to fit against the background.

Table 2. K/L conversion electron ratios measured for selected transitions, compared to predicted values based on BrIcc [12] and previous measurements of E0 intensities [4]. The predicted ratio for the 586 keV transition is presented without uncertainties, as BrIcc is unable to estimate the error in E0 electronic factors.

E (keV)	J_i^π	J_f^π	Multipolarity	Measured K/(L+M)	Predicted K/(L+M)
271	0_2^+	2_1^+	E2	2.7(3)	3.15(5)
344	2_1^+	0_1^+	E2	3.6(6)	3.73(5)
586	2_2^+	2_1^+	E2+M1+E0	2.9(5)	6.67

Table 3. Separate K/(L+M) ratios for each multipolarity component of the mixed E0+M1+E2 586 keV transition, along with the relative contribution of each component in terms of intensity, using predictions from BrICC [12] and previous measurements of the E0 relative intensity [4].

Multipolarity	Predicted K/(L+M)	Relative contribution
E0	7.12	0.71
M1	5.95	0.19
E2	4.87	0.10

The 271 keV transition, populating the 344 keV state, has K- and L-shell conversion electrons at 221 keV and 263 keV respectively. The coincidence gate on the 344 keV gamma ray allows these peaks to be clearly seen in figure 3, removing nearby peaks that otherwise impede fitting of the peaks of interest. The intensities of these peaks have been measured, assuming that the detector efficiency remains constant over the range in energies between the K and L peaks. Due to the low energy resolution of the Si(Li) detector, the M-shell electron peak cannot be resolved from the L-shell peak. As such, the measured K/L ratios are considered to represent the K/(L+M) intensity ratio and are compared to theoretical predictions accordingly.

Theoretical predictions of the K/(L+M) ratios can be obtained using BrIcc, a database of internal conversion coefficients and E0 electronic factors. We used the default BrIcc table, based on Dirac-Fock calculations using the Frozen Orbital approximation. The BrIcc predicted K/(L+M) ratios depend on the multipole character given for the transition; for the 271 keV and 344 keV transitions the evaluated data suggests a pure E2 character, while the 586 keV has a suggested E0+M1+E2 multipolarity. However, as BrIcc provides an electronic factor rather than an internal conversion coefficient for the E0 component of a mixed transition, the K/(L+M) ratio for 586 keV transition was considered separately for each multipolarity and recombined to give an overall ratio. Furthermore, as BrICC only gives K and L components of E0 transitions, the M-shell peak of the E0 component could not be included in this overall calculation.

An E2/M1 mixing ratio of $\delta = -3.05(14)$ was used to predict the K/L ratio for the 586 keV transition, as suggested in the evaluated data based on experimental measurements of the K-shell internal conversion coefficient [4, 13]. The ratio of E0 electronic factors for each shell given by BrIcc, and the ratio of E0 to M1+E2 internal conversion intensity given in the nuclear data, were used to calculate the overall K/(L+M) intensity ratio for the 586 keV transition. However, as BrIcc is unable to estimate errors on E0 electronic factors, the theoretical ratio for this transition has been presented without uncertainties.

The results of the K/(L+M) ratio measurements are given in table 2, with comparisons to theoretical predictions. For the 271 keV and 344 keV transitions, the measured values validate the theoretical predictions of internal conversion coefficients, supporting the pure E2 multipolarity assignment. However, there is a significant discrepancy between the measured and predicted values for the 586 keV transition that persists after correction for the E0 component and the unresolved M-shell peak.

The separate K/(L+M) ratios and relative contributions of each multipolarity component of the 586 keV transition are shown in table 3, each of which shows a larger K/(L+M) ratio than the measured value. The L+M peak has low statistics compared to the background, making peak fitting challenging, and the peak shows a larger width than other peaks at similar energies, suggesting that there may be a further unresolved electron peak contributing to the underestimated K/(L+M) ratio. The disagreement of each multipolarity component in table 3 with the measured value supports the conclusion that the discrepancy may be dominated by measurement error rather than an incorrect mixing ratio or relative E0 contribution.

Coincidence gates may also be placed on discrete-energy internal conversion electron peaks, with the resulting gamma-ray spectra shown in figure 4. The gamma rays identified in the electron-gated spectra correspond to those emitted in deexcitation cascades ending in the 344 keV E2 and 615 keV E0 transitions, both of which decay directly to the ^{152}Gd ground state. This serves to validate the electron peaks gated on the Si(Li) spectra, confirming their origin as K-shell conversion electrons emitted from the corresponding transitions in ^{152}Gd .

5. Discussion

The electron-gamma spectroscopy of ^{152}Tb has allowed for direct measurement of the relative intensities of E0 transitions, which are invisible to gamma-gamma spectroscopy setups. These intensities aid in level scheme building, contributing to the feeding in and out of excited states via electromagnetic transitions. The balance of transition intensity feeding in and out of excited states is valuable for inferring the beta decay strength, a significant contribution to the patient dose.

The measurement of internal conversion coefficients also supports this balancing of transition strength, representing a further contribution to the dosimetry calculations that cannot be measured using gamma-gamma spectroscopy alone. While internal conversion coefficients can be calculated from theory to a high degree of precision, these calculations require the multipolarity of transitions to be firmly established. The level scheme of

the decay of ^{152}Tb features many transitions of unknown multipolarity, the assignment of which may be made by comparing measured internal conversion coefficients to theoretical predictions.

The internal conversion electron emission intensity is particularly significant for dosimetry, as the short range of electrons compared to gamma rays leads to more of the transition energy being deposited in the patient's body. Internal conversion also gives rise to secondary Auger electron emissions, with potentially even shorter range and low kinetic energy. As a consequence, the range of Auger electrons in human tissue is usually of sub-cellular dimensions, with such a strongly localised deposition of energy leading to a significant biological effect [20]. Transitions with a higher internal conversion coefficient will therefore contribute proportionally more of their energy to the total absorbed dose, making the internal conversion coefficient a significant quantity to dosimetry calculations.

Theoretical predictions of internal conversion coefficients are well validated and provide high degrees of precision [12]. Our measurements have validated these predictions for several transitions, with our measurements of relative intensities improving on the precision of BrIcc predictions for the most intense transitions. Preliminary K/(L+M) ratio measurements show possible discrepancies from theoretical predictions, but require further analysis to quantify the impact of unresolved conversion electron peaks from neighbouring transitions and to ensure the applicability of BrIcc theoretical predictions for transitions with strong E0 components.

Less intense transitions are not easily resolved in the current data, and the measurement of their internal coefficients may not be possible. The validation of theoretical predictions and the assignment of multiplicities to low-intensity transitions may require a setup with higher efficiency and more statistics. Furthermore, a setup with the capability of gating on multiple gamma rays would improve the selectivity available and help mitigate the impact of unresolved electron peaks from unrelated transitions. However, the current setup is sufficient for the measurement of internal conversion coefficient and E0 transition strengths for the most intense transitions, which contribute the majority of the conversion electron dose in the decay.

6. Conclusion

Electron-gamma spectroscopy of the decay of ^{152}Tb supports the gamma-gamma spectroscopy of the same decay. Preliminary measurements of conversion electrons and E0 transitions have been used to validate the transition intensities recommended in the evaluated nuclear data for the 433 keV and 615 keV transitions. Further measurements of the K/(L+M) ratio of the 271 keV and 344 keV transitions have been compared to theoretical predictions based on BrIcc calculations, confirming the pure E2 multipole character of these transitions. Discrepancies between the measured and predicted K/(L+M) ratios for the 586 keV transition indicate the need for further analysis of these data.

These electrons are not measurable with the HPGe array used in the gamma-gamma spectroscopy experiment, and have an important role in mapping the level scheme of the decay. Accurate internal conversion coefficients are vital in balancing the feeding in and out of excited states in ^{152}Gd , in turn allowing the feeding of these states in the beta decay to be calculated. The determination of the beta strength function, and therefore the beta dose to patients, is a key aim of the gamma-gamma spectroscopy which this parallel experiment supports.

Internal conversion electrons are also an important contribution to the patient dose in their own right, depositing a higher proportion of the transition energy into the patient's body than gamma rays due to the short range of electrons. Auger electrons emitted following internal conversion may have ranges less than the size of an individual cell, with a strongly localised biological effect.

While this experiment is limited in its ability to detect low intensity transitions, the completed analysis will provide confirmation of predicted internal conversion coefficients and E0 transition strengths, supporting the decay spectroscopy of ^{152}Tb and the goal of providing accurate nuclear data for its clinical use.

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Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study will be openly available following an embargo at the following URL/DOI: <https://doi.ill.fr/10.5291/ILL-DATA.3-01-727>. Data will be available from 5 July 2026.

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